

The Role of African Religion in Fostering National Unity and Integration in Nigeria: The Tangle Religious Perspective

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Abstract

It is no longer news that Nigeria as one united political and geographical entity has continued to experience inter religious and inter-ethnic sentiments bickering, misunderstanding, mistrust which have constantly snowballed into crisis of tremendous proportion. As a result, many innocent lives and properties worth billions of naira have been lost. This ugly situation has continued to threaten the corporate existence of Nigeria and retrogressive affected the socioeconomic development of Nigeria. The paper aims at examining the role African Religion in fostering national unity and integration in Nigeria using the Tangle Religious Perspective. The paper identifies some factors threatening national unity and integration and also to examine the Tangle religious values that are capable of maintaining the peaceful coexistence and national unity needed in Nigeria. The paper adopts qualitative design. It relies on both primary and secondary sources. Descriptive and analytical approach will be used. The paper suggests that the subject of national integration must not be overlooked but it should be encouraged, embraced and put into practice by Nigerians in order to promote unity, integration and national development. The paper concludes that peaceful coexistence and national integration desired by Nigerians are realizable in the immediate and conscious return to traditional and socio religious values and morals which are the foundation for genuine conscience and national development.

Keywords: Unity, integration, Tangle, national development

Introduction

National integration or unity in a pluralistic society like Nigeria has been a problematic issue since attainment of independent in 1960. It is no longer news that Nigeria as one united political and geographical entity has continued to experience inter religious and inter-ethnic sentiments bickering, misunderstanding, mistrust which have constantly snowballed into crisis of tremendous proportion. As a result, many innocent lives and properties worth billions of naira have been lost. This ugly situation has continued to threaten the corporate existence of Nigeria and retrogressive affected the socioeconomic development of Nigeria. This has over the years made the task of building a united nation out of the heterogeneous ethnic and religious groups' one of the greatest challenges facing political leaders.

In most plural societies, the promotion of national integration is often a conscious agenda of the state. Usually, policies are pursued that will encourage individual and group allegiance to the state and its institutions as opposed to sub-national ethnic, religious or other group loyalties. As Pius Adejoh notes, "The object usually is to create patriotic citizens out of disparate, often antagonistic groups."¹ In post-colonial Nigeria state, national integration embodies a strategy of forging unity in diversity, and connotes a striving to be a unified people in a modern, colonially created, nation-state.² Because there is now a multiplicity of religions in the country, some of which do not even fit into the three dominant religions, it has become necessary to exploit the opportunity of these religions for the task of national integration.

Conceptual Clarification

This section seeks to clarify concepts that might pose ambiguity in the course of their usage in the paper:

African Religion

African traditional religion consists the religious beliefs and practices of the Africans. As Joseph Omosade Awolalu explains, it is the religion which resulted from the sustaining faith held by the fore bearers of the present Africans and which is being practiced today in various forms, shades and intensities, by a large number of Africans; including individuals who claim to be Muslims or Christians.³ African religion is called African because it is indigenous, aboriginal and foundational or handed down from generation to generation.⁴ The religion is part and parcel of African life. It was founded by the Africans and is handed on from one generation to another by words of mouth. Not only that the religion has been in existence long before the advent of Islam and Christianity on the continent, it is practiced by the Africans on the African soil and those in the diaspora. According to Sarwuan Daniel Shishima, African religion is said to be traditional due to many factors. First and foremost; it is traditional because it is a religion and culture that is based on the life of the Africans. This pattern of life has been handed on from their fore fathers from generation to generation. Its mode of worship, articles of faith, materials used for worship in temples, shrines and holy places are all from the African local environment.⁵

National Unity and Integration

The terms “national integration,” “nation-building,” “national loyalty and national cohesion” are sometimes interchangeably used to refer to national unity. Chang L.W, Azizan, B and Amran, M articulated that national unity is described as the processes that bring together the entire community and nation to build a shared interest and oneness identity to love, and to be full of pride of the country.⁶ National integration involves the processes that produce national identity in terms of cultural, social and political position among a separate group. National integration, according to Jega Mohammad Atahiru⁷ is a condition whereby the country citizens more and more see themselves as a single nation, conjoin by common historical occurrences and shared ideals, and instilled with the character of loyalty and solidity that go beyond conventional ancient varied leanings. E. Edosa sees the idea of national integration to be a process in which the representatives of a state consider themselves like one people, treat each other equally and collaborate in a cooperative and free manner and make a peaceful resolution of their differences for the nation’ interest as a whole.⁸ In this way, unity, fair treatment, co-operation, consensus, and peaceful conflict-resolution become essential components of loyalty to the nation. Through this, appropriate treatment, teamwork, compromise, unity and peaceful resolution of disputes thus become the indispensable mechanism of allegiance to the nation.

R.O. Arisi asserts that national integration is a type of mutual support that involves uniting different societal groupings by way of a collective identity, setting aside key disparities, but simultaneously not disregarding each group’s unique character.⁹ This implies that national unity can be achieved through socialization processes such as the use of a uniform education system, the same language, and inter-marriage practices. For Adeoyo Muhammad Nasiru, national integration refers to the process of bringing diverse cultural and social groups into a single territorial unit and the establishment of a national unity. It is the progressive removal of antagonisms and reduction of cultural and regional decisions and differences in the process of creating a homogenous political unit.¹⁰

To Adejoh, the term presumes the existence of an ethnically plural society in which each group is characterized by its own language, or other self-conscious cultural qualities, which generate the problem of creating a sense of territorial nationality, which overshadows or eliminates subordinate parochial loyalties.¹¹ Similarly, C.E. Okonkwo defines it as the process of opening up a group, community, place of organization, to all, regardless of race, ethnicity, religion, gender or social class.¹² He expresses the view that: “at the heart of meaningful integration must lie a deep understanding of the relative importance of the value systems, customs,

religion and behaviour of the various groupings.”¹³ This implies the weakening of certain types of ethnocentric tendencies as well as positive moves as well as positive moves to build new relationships or fortify existing ones.

The essential task of national integration is that of building cohesion amongst the various ethnic and religious groups or it can be said to aim at fostering higher loyalties in the place of parochial loyalties to the ethnic or religious origin of the citizens. National integration is used to describe a process of ensuring that the component parts (ethnic nationalities) of a nation are brought together to achieve a higher sense of belonging, mutual understanding and nationalism.

The Tangle Traditional Religious Beliefs

The Tangle of Gombe State are a very religious people. Religion preceded in everything they do. It colours their speech and deeds. Indeed Religion dictates their family, social, political, military and economic life.”¹⁴ Tangle religion is as old as the Tangle people themselves and is woven around a supreme deity known as *Yamba*. *Yamba* (Supreme Being) is a being associated with things older than their ages and supersedes their imagination.”¹⁵ Pero Billiri posits that *Yamba* is also used by other neighbouring ethnic groups of the Tangle such as Kamu, Waja.¹⁶ Stephen Hall, one of the pioneer missionaries in Tangle land expressed his view about the Tangle notion of God thus: “there is a definite and unquestionable belief in the existence of a Supreme Being. His name is *Yamba*, in the sentence *Yamba ne* (God exists), used constantly in oaths and affirmations, the Supreme Being’s existence, knowledge and authority are acknowledged.”¹⁷ Therefore, the Tangle belief in a Supreme Being or *Yamba* who is the creator of all that exist and resides in the sky heavens; as the phrase *Yambam ta kwi tong*.

Religion and the Quest for National Integration in Nigeria

The question of national integration in Nigeria arises as a result of the multi-ethnic and pluralist religious nature of the country. In fact, religion has served as a means of unifying the different ethnic and political groups in the country. Nigerian governments have promoted national integration which reflects and encourages multiplicity of religion. Instances of these are evident in a number of constitutional provisions, which guarantee against religious discrimination and marginalisation. A.S. Ayinla notes that Nigerian Constitution has so far attempted to forge unity through the diversity of religion. To a large extent, state machineries have been used and public funds have been expended to strengthen religions and forge national integration. Examples abound. The observance of religious holidays like *Eid Fitr*, *Eid Kabir*, Easter and Christmas among others is a unifying factor for different ethnic groups.¹⁸ More so, public oath based on the Qur’an and Bible as well as official requests by the Government that Muslims and Christians should offer prayers on certain occasions also testify to the use of religion as a unifying factor.

It is also fashionable that during festive periods, Muslim, Christian and political leaders exchange greetings.¹⁹ In addition, the two dominant religions (Islam and Christianity) in Nigeria play significant role in the life of their adherents and the nation at large through the various welfare programmes; for example, Catholic Health Project and Federation of Muslim Women Association of Nigeria (FOMWAN) readily come to mind here. Some other religious groups have similar projects. Furthermore, religion has also served as a unifying factor during the periods of national crises, especially the civil war. Onyiaji B.C. and Adeoye, M.N. examined the role which the different Christian denominations played before and during the civil war. The same can be said of some Muslim organizations and mosques across the country. These are some of the ways by which the various religious groups in the country contribute to national integration.²⁰

Despite the above efforts of religion in contributing to national integration, religion is also known to have played a pivotal role to the country’s challenge for national integration and unity. Sharing this sentiment, Nweke Innocent asserts that: “agitations for recognition by various ethnic groups, resource control, ethno-religious politics and other primordial cleavages have crept into national consciousness of many Nigerians”.²¹ This development motivated various past administrations or regimes to establish national integration programmes like

National Youth Service Scheme (NYSC), Unity Schools, National Orientation Agency, National Sports and Cultural Festivals amongst others.²² These efforts have not yielded the desired result. Part of the challenge in this direction is the manipulation of religion by the political elites.

S. Adamu states that in Nigeria, the entire gamut of social, political and economic relations revolves around Islam and Christianity, and this has been the basis of legitimacy for the political class. In their quest for power and to enhance their prospects of capturing and retaining it for their environment, religion is used.²³ Notable politicians have used or known to sponsor misguided extremists in causing disturbance which has led to conflicts between Christians and Muslims resulting in the death of many. S. Adamu reiterates thus:

It is for this reason that many have come to believe that the Boko Haram insurgency is a political tool to score political points. During the 2015 general elections, it does appear the Northern elites have agreed to put the Presidency under siege, believing that by doing so, they would put at a political advantage by instigating religious and ethnic sentiments in a multi-religious and ethnic country like Nigeria in order to capture power by all means.²⁴

Consequently, religion which should have been a unifying factor has been manipulated to cause division and hatred. Evidences abound in pages of newspapers and magazines, of irresponsible and inflammatory remarks made at one time or the other by prominent Nigerian Muslim or Christian politicians. Thus, democratic values such as dialogue, national unity, patriotism, self-reliance, territorial integrity and political consciousness are in most cases, not practiced or promoted. Political leaders have continued to exploit the country's religious and regional diversity to create and consolidate political base of support. In doing so, integration among people became a problem. The consequence is that Nigeria today is a deeply divided society in terms of religion.

Fostering National Unity and Integration in Nigeria: The Tangle Traditional Religious Perspective

The Tangle traditional religion ensures a harmonious society by not advocating for conversion to other religions like Islam or Christianity (which creates suspicion and tension). Values and morals are the aspects of African Traditional Religion which deal with the ideas that defend or sustain the life of the people in their relationship with one another and the world around them. Cover issues like justice, right and wrong, respect for people and prosperity, truth, love, good and evil, the keeping of promises and agreements, beauty, crime and punishment, praise and blame, etc. Values and morals are the aspects of African Traditional Religion which deal with the ideas that defend or sustain the life of the people in their relationship with one another and the world around them. Values and morals cover issues like justice, right and wrong, respect for people and prosperity, truth, love, good and evil, the keeping of promises and agreements, beauty, crime and punishment, praise and blame, etc. Values and morals are the aspects of African Traditional Religion which deal with the ideas that defend or sustain the life of the people in their relationship with one another and the world around them. Values and morals cover issues like justice, right and wrong, respect for people and prosperity, truth, love, good and evil, the keeping of promises and agreements, beauty, crime and punishment, praise and blame, etc. These values and morals determine the political, economic and social behaviour of a people and stability and development of any nation of the world. It is in this light that Mbon writes that, the development or otherwise of a nation to a very great amount depends on the moral and intellectual development or otherwise of its people (101-109). Supporting this assertion, Anyanwu observes succinctly that, we are not quite aware that any society can afford to exist in the absence of morality, trust, justice, liberty, truth, goodness and faithfulness. Only religion provides these (11).

We can therefore deduce from above assertions as follows: that for any nation or society to experience justice, trust, love, peace and harmony, its citizens must be imbued with all the good life and qualities provided by

religion (African Traditional Religion) through its moral education. Again, African Traditional Religion teaches its adherents to eschew evil, bribery, corruption, ethnicity, tribalism and nepotism. These teachings are bedrock for national development.

This is a humble call to Nigerian government and its citizens to return to their traditional socio-religions values and morals system which is a catalyst that will bring change in our characters and attitudes and thereby giving birth to the needed development in Nigeria. For there seems to be no other way through which Nigeria can come out of their present moral dilemma which enhances corruption, tribalism, nepotism, ethnicity, bribery and assassination. The moral salvation of Nigerians lies only in their immediate return to their traditional socio-religious values and morals system which is the foundation for genuine conscience and National developmental values and morals are important aspects of African Traditional Religion which deal with the ideas that defend or sustain the life of the people in their relationship with one another and the world around them; and the Tangle traditional religion is not an exception. Ekeopara and Ekpenyong explain that values and morals cover issues like justice, right and wrong, respect for people and prosperity, truth, love, good and evil, the keeping of promises and agreements, beauty, crime and punishment, praise and blame, among others ⁴⁵ Similarly, Ernest Anyacho concisely outlines the constituent elements of values in a wide range of virtues such as: honesty, integrity, chastity, vivacity, modesty, tolerance, truthfulness, self-discipline, humility, patience, industry etc. These are laudable virtues which every ideal society tries to inculcate in its members.⁴⁶ Values induce man to choose one thing and not the other and determine his behaviour and means of attaining a choice. Values are present everywhere in man's life. They determine his choice and decision making. Values can be brought about by either society or individual. The value system of a people metamorphoses into the culture of the people⁴³. Anibueze, G.U. distinguishes between high and low values. High values according to him are those values which are noble, altruistic and unselfish in nature e.g., justice, benevolence, friendship, truth, goodness, love, honesty, peace, beauty, freedom etc. while low or base values are those values which are selfish, ignoble and cannot go beyond an individuals' personality. Examples here include: greed, violence, envy, hatred and any act which is adverse to the well-being and happiness of all the people in the society.⁴⁴ Values are fundamental in all human societies and in human actions and activities. Generally, morality originates from religious considerations, and so pervasive is religion in Nigerian culture that the two cannot be separated. What constitutes moral code of any particular society; the laws, taboos, customs and set forms of behaviour all derive their compelling power from religion. Thus, morality flows out of religion, and through this the conduct of individuals are regulated; and any break of the moral code is regarded as evil and punishable.

Gaius Alhassan reports that in Tangle religion, "most of the important virtues are either couched in proverbs or expressed in the form of a folk-tale with a moral to it" (oral interview) ²⁵. The proverbs may serve as prescriptions for action or act as judgment in times of moral lapses. Proverbs are often cited at appropriate times during an argument, can settle the dispute instantly, for the proverbs are believed to have been handed down by the ancestors and predecessors to whom the Tangle owe their communal experience and wisdom. Thus, in Tangle traditional religion, adherents learn positive values like hard work, commitment and diligence from the traditional religious leaders. These traditional value systems aimed at changing and transforming the people to develop patriotism and love their people and sacrifice everything for the common good of their society. Abur, E.C. and Apeku Solomon captured this aptly when they wrote that values and morals determine the political, economic and social behaviour of a people and stability of any nation of the world.

Supporting this assertion, Anyanwu Herbert Onyema affirms that "we are not quite aware that any society can afford to exist in the absence of morality, trust, justice, liberty, truth, goodness and faithfulness. Only religion provides these."²⁷ Therefore, for any nation or society to experience justice, trust, love, peace and harmony, its citizens must be imbued with all the good life and qualities provided by African Traditional Religion through its moral education. For instance, Ladi Sidi says, "the Tangle Traditional Religion teaches its adherents to eschew evil, bribery, greed, corruption, deceit, ethnicity, tribalism and nepotism."²⁸ These teachings are bedrock for national unity and integration.

Besides, it should be noted that the Tangle traditional religion has high value for human life, and as such killing of human beings is met with grave consequences on the part of the offender. The religion also places love of one another in high esteem. For instance, the religion does not discriminate; it welcomes all individuals willing to participate in its worship voluntarily and this love has the potentials of breaking sectional barriers in Nigeria. Osam Edwin contends that “nothing can change a mind better than love.”²⁹

In the same vein, Tangle traditional religion emphasizes love, fairness, honesty, respect among others which is enunciated in peace and justice: while opposing oppression and injustice of any sort. The spirit beings such as *Anampidok*, *Anantawe* and *Anaye* do play useful roles in regulating human behaviour through their protection and punishment of evil doers in society, thereby ensuring that peace and unity is sustained. Therefore, the Tangle traditional religion has the leverage and capacity to drive away the rottenness of injustice, corruption and ethnicity, which have continued to clog the wheel of Nigerian unity.

It is unfortunate there are incessant cases of injustices, corruption and oppression being perpetrated by some elements in Nigeria. The recent killing of Deborah Samuel, a 200L student of Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto is a testament to the fact that adherents who are not of the traditional religious faith lack tolerance and respect for the sanctity of human life. This incident has widened disharmony and has heightened tensions in the socio-religious arena of an already volatile and precarious religious situation in Nigeria with the potential of instigating riots. The reason behind the deteriorating situation is not far-fetched. This is because of the changing value systems which the society came to adopt. In the words of Agbe, Nancy it is a pity that the Nigeria society is fast bearing a ‘mixed’ society’ where even condemnable acts are tolerated.³⁰

Divination, which is a feature of Tangle traditional religion is very useful in revealing causes of mishap in the community. This method of finding causes of mysterious happenings is more reliable than investigations that are done in most cases without any reasonable result. In most cases, atrocities are committed and security agencies are asked to fish out those behind a crime and they fail to do so. This cannot be so when a divination is involved. This is because the Tangle traditional religion has divine injunctions and penalties for contravening such injunctions, as such prescriptions and disciplinary measures are executed through the intermediaries such as the king, divinities, ancestors and elders. Perhaps, it is in this light that Friday Mbon writes:

Unless Nigeria goes back to, and begins to put into practice, traditional ethical principles, principles based on the communal concern for the well-being of all, and not only for the well-being of a privileged few; principles based on kinship or lineage relationships, and a “big brother” concept, within which configuration those who had more shared what they had with those who had less. Principles founded not on the ethics of individualism and human autonomy and selfishness, but on a common unity-centered, theonomous, theocentric and ancestor sanctioned set of ethical criteria.³¹

Thus, in Tangle traditional religion individuals strive to be morally upright since any form of laxity would result in sanctions. If this is done, it will act as a form of checks and balances between members and leaders of our great nation, Nigeria, thereby removing all the road blocks to national unity and integration such as corruption, nepotism, tribalism, bribery, embezzlement, and it will similarly aid good behaviour in people. It is only then that Nigeria as a nation can begin to say at least that it has taken a step in the right direction to national unity and integration.

Recommendations

Having examined the issues involved in this study, the following recommendations are made:

Re-entrenchment of positive values of traditional African society: There is need for the re-entrenchment of positive values of traditional African society, especially Tangle trado-religious moral values for the sustenance of democracy in Nigeria. These positive values are values which stress proper social and human relations, pre-eminence of the community and individual virtues. These positive values include: Justice, peace,

order, harmony, cooperation, unity, honesty, love, understanding, respect for community, sportsmanship, tolerance, good neighbourliness, humanness, equity, self-control, patriotism, communalism, loyalty, punctuality, wisdom, craftiness, fidelity, bravery, humility, truth, kindness, patience. These values places emphasis on the group rather than on the individual, more on solidarity than on the activity and needs of the individual, more on communion of persons than on their autonomy.

Treaties and Covenant via rituals: The Tangle adore, revere, and respect their deities greatly. Treaties and covenant via rituals are used to foster peace and harmony. The reason for this is build trust, abate fears and to discourage lack of peace in the community.

Informal education: The Tangle people educate her citizens through proverbs, storytelling, riddles and jocks, myths, poems etc. through parents, guardians, folktales. They educate to be of moral standard, they discourage laziness, theft, covetousness, insincerity, cruelty, incest, aggression, violence and hostility.

Socialization through Festivals: Socialization is cardinal to Tangle ethical, moral and cognitive development. Through festivals Tangle sons and daughters far and near including visitors attend to celebrate as part of their culture. The young learn from old ones.

Traditional and Religious leaders: The Traditional and Religious leaders of the various faith groups should not only preach peace but sensitize their adherents on the importance of living in peace and harmony in each gathering. They should ensure that they are honest in all their dealings and also adhere to the rules and regulations of the land.

Conclusion

From the foregone discussion, it is worthy to note that the achievement of national unity and integration depends upon individuals in developing national consciousness as a conscious decision. It requires deliberate policy and efforts. The nation is not a given. It can only arise as a result of conscious effort, an existential choice which enables man to escape from natural determinants. Therefore, this is a humble call to Nigerian government and its citizens to return to their traditional socio-religions values and morals system which is a catalyst that will bring change in our characters and attitudes and thereby giving birth to the needed national unity and integration in Nigeria. For there seems to be no other way through which Nigeria can come out of their present moral dilemma which enhances corruption, tribalism, nepotism, ethnicity, bribery and assassination which hinders national unity and integration. The moral salvation of Nigerians lies only in their immediate return to their traditional socio-religious values and morals system which is the foundation for genuine conscience and national integration.

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